

Brain, Mind and Soul in Dyslexia: A Conceptual Review

Deepa Peethambaran^{1*}, Lekshmi M. K²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Ayurvedic Paediatrics, MVR Ayurveda Medical College, Parassinikadavu P.O, Kannur, Kerala, India, Pin – 670 563

²Associate Professor, Department of Ayurvedic Paediatrics, Govt. Ayurveda College, Trivandrum, Kerala, India- 695012

***Corresponding Author: Deepa Peethambaran**

ABSTRACT: Learning is a psychological process that includes sensation, perception, thinking and memory. Dyslexia, which is characterized by problems with accurate or fluent word recognition, poor decoding, and poor spelling abilities and the main deficit will be in phonological awareness. It is a lifelong condition and is managed only through remedial learning techniques. Dyslexia in Ayurveda can be seen as a disturbance where *mana* and *buddhi* fail to properly process and integrate sensory information with memory. Our literature review included a comprehensive search of Ayurveda textbooks and online databases such as PubMed, Scopus and Google Scholar. The objective was to interpret dyslexia using Ayurvedic principles and to provide a detailed understanding of its *samprapti* (etiopathology), with special reference to phonological awareness and to develop a management protocol. Although dyslexia is not mentioned explicitly in Ayurveda classics its features suggest impairment in cognition stages of *Jnanotpathikrama* (process of cognition and knowledge acquisition) particularly at *indriyatha sannikarsha* (association of sense organs with their objects) and during the analytical processing performed by *buddhi* (intellect), aided by *mana* (mind). Certain principles of *Unmada Chikitsa* may be applicable in dyslexia due to the involvement of cognitive and perceptual dysfunctions, with *Buddhi Vibhrama* being a central feature in *Unmada Samprapti* and *Buddhi* playing an important role in dyslexia. The Ayurvedic perspective highlights the integration of sensory organs, mind, intellect, and consciousness in knowledge acquisition.

KEYWORDS: Specific learning disorder, Dyslexia, Phonemic awareness, *Indriyatha sannikarsha*, *Jnanotpathikrama*

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning depends entirely on cognitive processes¹. Knowledge is acquired through the cognitive process, including perception, reasoning, evaluation, judging, and remembrance. The frontal lobe and prefrontal cortex are the primary areas of the brain that contribute to cognition². Specific learning disability [SLD], as per DSM 5, is a type of neurodevelopmental Disorder that impedes the ability to learn or use specific academic skills (e.g., reading, writing, or arithmetic), which are the foundation for other academic learning. SLD is an umbrella term that can describe many learning issues. The term "specific" in specific learning disability indicates that it is not due to visual or auditory abnormalities or low intelligence issues.

Dyslexia is the most prevalent kind of SLD, with a prevalence range of 5-17.5% worldwide as per DSM-5 and DSM-5-TR³, in which even a child with an average or above IQ struggles with phonological

awareness and word recognition, resulting in reduced reading efficiency and poor academic performance. According to the Dyslexia Association of India, research showed that 10–15% of Indian children are dyslexic⁵. Dysgraphia and dyscalculia are the other types of SLD. In the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th edition (DSM-5), dysgraphia is defined as "impairment in written expression and dyscalculia is categorized as a specific learning disorder (SLD) that affects maths skills⁴.

As per Ayurveda, the mind, body, and soul function as a tripod. The mind serves as a connection between the body and the soul. Knowledge is perceived through the combined participation of the *jnanendriyas* (sense organs), *manas* (mind), *buddhi* (intellect), and *athma* (soul)⁵. Object perception occurs in the corresponding sense organ and is transmitted to the mind. *Mana*, with its karmas such as *chinthya* (thought), *vicharya* (consideration), and *oohya* (hypothesis), transmits perceptual knowledge to *buddhi*. The various components of *buddhi*, such as *dhee* (intelligence), *dhriti* (patience), *smriti* (memory) and *medha* (power of retention), aid in distinguishing between correct and incorrect knowledge and recalling memories, thus impelling an individual to speak or act intelligently⁶.

Dyslexia in the Ayurveda context can be viewed as a dysfunction in the chain of knowledge perception—specifically at the junction where *mana* and *buddhi* integrate sensory input with stored memory. The equilibrium of the *tridoshas*, *indriyarthasannikarsha* and optimal functioning of *dhee*, *smriti*, and *dhriti* are essential for fluent reading and comprehension. As *medha* is a part of *dhee* the derangement of *dhee* is also applicable for *medha*-storage of perceived knowledge. When any of these factors are impaired—especially the *samyukta samaveta samavaya sannikarsha*—difficulties in decoding written language, as seen in dyslexia, are likely to occur. As there is no definitive treatment for dyslexia, a holistic approach may offer better support, especially when its etiopathogenesis is interpreted through Ayurveda with particular emphasis on phonological awareness.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study employed a systematic approach to identify and synthesize literature that bridges the cognitive mechanisms of dyslexia with Ayurvedic cognitive frameworks.

2.1 Search strategy

A comprehensive search was conducted across online databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar, along with a manual search of classical Ayurveda textbooks. While this review spans a broad spectrum of papers, including seminal 20th-century studies, it prioritizes works published within the last decade, up to April 2025. To ensure a thorough review, we did not impose any constraints on study location, or participant characteristics, aiming to identify the maximum number of relevant publications.

2.2 Data extraction

Identification: A total of 16,198 records were initially identified using the broad term SLD.

Screening: After removing duplicates and filtering by publication year (post-1985), 13,872 records remained. These were screened by title and abstract. At this stage, keywords were used to narrow the focus to Dyslexia (7,632) and specifically Phonemic Awareness (257) to ensure relevance to the review's core objective.

Articles were excluded if they predominantly focused on management, therapeutic interventions, remediation techniques, or outcome-based treatment protocols for dyslexia or SLD, were survey-based studies emphasizing prevalence, screening tools, or questionnaire validation without etiological or cognitive discussion, lacked relevance to the etiopathological understanding of phonemic awareness deficits, could not be meaningfully correlated with the Ayurveda framework of cognition, particularly concepts related to *indriyarthasannikarsha*, *mana*, and *buddhi*.

Inclusion: A final set of 60 papers was selected for qualitative synthesis. These provided the necessary insights into the cognitive mechanisms of dyslexia and the Ayurvedic understanding of sensory perception and intellectual integration.

This structured stepwise exclusion ensured that the final set of articles was highly focused, conceptually relevant, and aligned with the objective of examining dyslexia primarily through the lens of phonemic awareness and its possible Ayurveda correlation, rather than management-oriented perspectives. It is depicted in Figure 1.

3. RESULT

3.1 Knowledge perception from the foetal stage

It is explained that an individual's learning ability is determined right when one's life gets seeded in his mother's womb. The development of *buddhi* starts in the sixth month of intrauterine development⁷. People's mental faculties can be influenced by their past actions. *Athmaja bhavas* [traits derived from the soul] and *satwaja bhavas* [traits derived from the mind], which are responsible for procreation, will help to form the components of *buddhi* and *manas* properly⁷. *Athmaja bhavas* bring forward the subtle essence of one's spiritual identity, while *satwaja bhavas* contribute to the purity, clarity, and strength of the mind. For these faculties to develop harmoniously, the intrauterine environment must be supportive and balanced. The wholesomeness of the mother's food and activities during pregnancy forms the *satmyaja bhava* [traits derived from the influence of the mother's diet, habits, and lifestyle during pregnancy], which contributes to the formation of the *medha*. Daytime sleep and alcohol consumption will impair the formation of the progeny's *buddhi*⁶.

Also, the most important factor, *prakriti*, which is formed based on the predominance of *dosha* at the time of fertilization, plays an important role in the formation of cognitive abilities. *Chala buddhi* (fluctuation intellect), *smriti*, and *dhrithi* are caused by the *chalatwa* attribute of *vata dosha*. The foods we eat influence the formation of mental characters such as *satwa*, *raja*, and *tama*.

3.2 Dyslexia from the conventional perspective

Dyslexia is the most prevalent type of SLD. It is of 2 types: acquired (due to injury to the brain) and developmental. Here, we account for developmental dyslexia (DD). According to the World Health Organization's (WHO) most recent classification (ICD-11), it is currently known as a developmental learning disorder with impairment in reading and is defined by significant and persistent difficulties in learning academic skills related to reading, such as word reading accuracy, reading fluency, and reading comprehension. It markedly affects performance in reading and is not due to "a disorder of intellectual development, sensory impairment (vision or hearing), neurological disorder, lack of availability of education, lack of proficiency in the language of academic instruction, or psychosocial adversity"⁸. Developmental dyslexia can be classified into at least two categories: surface and phonological. Reading irregular words is challenging for people with surface dyslexia, while difficulties with pseudo words typify phonological dyslexia. Of the two, phonological dyslexia is the more prevalent⁹. The exact cause of dyslexia is not known. A causal model comprising three levels of explanation—biological, cognitive, and behavioural—was stated to explain the causes of DD¹⁰. Abnormalities of the brain and genes contribute to the biological level. It has been suggested that the genes *DYX1C1*, *K1AA0319*, *DCDC2*, and *ROBO1* impact the development of developmental dyslexia¹¹. A cerebellar deficit¹² and a defect in the magnocellular pathways¹³—which are in charge of the quick input transmission from the retina to the occipital and parietal brain areas—are also contributing factors to brain abnormalities that fall under the biological level¹⁴.

Both the phonological deficit theory¹⁵ and the double deficit theory¹⁶ [incorporates both the phonological and name deficit theories] contribute to cognitive level¹⁷. The former includes poor phonological

awareness and verbal short-term memory, resulting in poor reading. The abnormal responses in the left inferior frontal, left parietal-temporal, and left inferior temporal-occipital regions can be used to address phonological deficits¹⁸. Studies have also shown that people with dyslexia have some left-right hemisphere asymmetry¹⁹. People with dyslexia have insufficient left hemisphere perisylvian region, which is primarily involved in language processing. The theory of cerebellar deficit can also be considered at the behavioural level²⁰.

Although screenings for dyslexia can start in kindergarten, a formal assessment is typically carried out starting at age 7. By 6 to 7 years, most children are ready to sound out words and begin reading simple books. One characteristic of certain learning disorders is a poor response to treatment²¹. Dyslexia can only be managed through remedial therapy, which includes grapheme-phoneme conversion exercises, lexical spelling tasks, and phonological awareness tasks²². Many schools, especially in rural areas, do not have enough facilities or trained teachers for remedial education. These programs are often expensive and time-consuming, so some families cannot afford them. Also, not all children benefit equally—some improve a lot, while others show only small improvement. Therefore, applying Ayurvedic principles to explain the etiopathogenesis of dyslexia may help in developing an Ayurvedic treatment approach, as this holistic science offers many formulations that can influence and support higher brain centers.

3.3 Dyslexia from ayurveda perspective

Ayurveda explains *jnanothpathikrama* as a complex interactive process between *indriyas*, *indriyarthas*, *mana*, *buddhi* and *athma*, which are controlled by *tridoshas* and *trigunas*. A knowledge seeker is essential for accurate knowledge acquisition. Here, the *jeevathma* (empirical soul), is the knower⁶. According to *Caraka*, *athma* initiates the process of acquiring knowledge. Ultimately, the knowledge reaches the individual soul, the *jeevathma*.

Even with a knower and an object of knowledge, knowledge perception is only possible if there is a trustworthy source of knowledge, namely *Pramanas*. Direct perceptions grounded in *buddhi*, which arises from the coordinated interaction of the individual *ātman*, *manas*, *indriyas*, and *indriyarthas*. As stated by *Caraka*, the *athma* possesses the ability to perceive, but this ability is only manifested when it is associated with the mind, intellect, and sensory organs. The combination of sense faculties, their objects, the mind, and the soul gives rise to *panchendriya buddhi*, the integrated awareness of the five senses. In Ayurveda practice, *indriyarthas sannikarsha* is used to understand the intricate relationships between the sense faculties, their objects, and the mind²³. Only with the involvement of *mana*, the cognisor *athma*, can perceive the knowledge collected by the sense organs. Even though *mana* is the master of sense organs, it is controlled by the *tridoshas* mainly *vata dosha*²⁴.

Buddhi helps to transform indeterminate knowledge into determinate knowledge. The definite cognition arises from determination. *Acharya Bhela* describes *buddhi vaisheshika alochaka pitha* as a subtle, luminous centre that illuminates the intellect and facilitates discernment, insight, and higher states of consciousness. It is located between the brows, where the third eye - *Ajna Chakra* and *sthapani marma* are situated. From an Ayurvedic perspective, this concept may be interpreted as symbolically corresponding to higher-order cognitive and perceptual functions²⁵. However, any correlation between *Ajna Chakra* and specific neuroanatomical structures should be considered hypothetical and requires further scientific investigation.

Buddhi contains three components: *dhee*, *dhriti*, and *smriti*. *Dhee* helps to understand things as they are, whereas *dhriti* helps to prevent the *mana* from engaging in uncontrolled activities. *Smriti* is the present recollection of some past cognition. It is a mental function that does not require using sense organs for recall. The *manovahasrothas* (subtle channels of mind) transmit the stored information to the mind, which then

interprets and analyses the information using the *buddhi*. Thus it can conclude that in *buddhi*, *dhriti* is responsible for acquiring knowledge and *medha*, *dhee* and *smriti* are responsible for processing knowledge.

The above sequence represents the normal physiological process of knowledge acquisition. When this framework is applied to the etiopathogenesis of dyslexia, it becomes evident that the disturbance primarily occurs at the level of *indriyārtha sannikarsha* and at the level of *buddhi*. It is depicted in Figure 2. In dyslexia, the *jeevathma* remains intact and there is no defect in the essential cognitive potential of the individual. However, due to impaired sensory processing and defective intellectual discrimination, the final outcome of the knowledge-acquisition process is compromised. As a result, the individual ultimately receives knowledge that is distorted or incomplete, manifesting as difficulties in reading, comprehension, and learning.

4. DISCUSSIONS

Reading is a complex skill involving two major components: decoding and comprehension. Decoding refers to reading words accurately and fluently, while comprehension refers to understanding the meaning of what is read²⁶. Decoding relies heavily on phonological awareness, especially the understanding of phonemes, the smallest units of sound in a language²⁷. A child can pronounce words correctly only when they understand the relationship between letters and sounds. Another important factor is the recognition of sight words—words that can be read instantly without sounding them out, such as “the” and “and.” Strong sight-word knowledge significantly improves reading fluency^{27,28}.

Working memory is also crucial. It allows a child to retain information while processing new information, such as remembering a recipe while cooking²⁹. In reading, working memory helps the child recall letter-sound patterns and apply them when encountering rhyming or unfamiliar words. Children with dyslexia often have difficulties with phonemic awareness, sight-word identification, and working memory. These challenges affect spelling, decoding unfamiliar words, and overall reading fluency. As a result, they may skip, add, or misread words, leading to reduced comprehension³⁰.

4.1 Stages of cognitive processing and dyslexia

In the case of reading, the sequence of events begins when the visual sense organ perceives a printed letter on a page. This can be interpreted as the first step, corresponding to *indriyārtha sannikarsha*—the contact between the sense organ and the sense object. In a typically developing child, the next stage involves *akshara rupatva jnana*, or the recognition of the form of the letter. Following this, the letter is mentally connected to its corresponding *shabda rupa* (phoneme or sound), allowing the child to read and comprehend the text. In dyslexia, while the first step—seeing the printed letter and identify the letter in the second stage—occurs normally. The difficulty arises following that, in mapping the letter to its sound. This specific dysfunction can be explained in Ayurveda terms as a disturbance in *samyukta samaveta samavāya sannikarsha* (conjunctant-concomitant inseparable –concomitance), where the seamless coordination between visual perception, memory recall, and phonemic association is impaired.

4.2 Second level of cognition and *buddhi*'s role

After the initial perception, the mind serves as the connecting bridge between the sensory input and the higher faculties of *buddhi*. At the second level of cognition, *buddhi* must perform analytical processing—matching the seen letter to its stored phonemic representation, interpreting it in context, and integrating it with previous knowledge. In dyslexia, despite having an average or above-average IQ, children often display working memory deficits (relating to *Smriti* and *medha*), difficulty in retaining sight words, and a reduced ability to sustain attention on decoding tasks (relating to *dhriti*). *Dhee*'s capacity to analyse and integrate letter-sound links is impaired.

4.3 *Satwika bhavas* and Cognitive Clarity

Ayurveda emphasizes that for accurate and efficient perception of knowledge, the *satwika bhavas* of all *antakaranas* (internal faculties) must be dominant. *Satwa* represents clarity, lightness, and truthfulness, and when it predominates, cognition becomes sharp and precise. In contrast, excess *raja* or *tama* can cloud the intellect, delay processing, and distort perception.

The *tridoṣas*—*Vata*, *Pitha*, and *Kapha*—also play an important role in maintaining this equilibrium. Balanced *doshas* support proper sensory function, mental clarity, and memory stability. Vitiating of *doshas*, especially *Vata* (responsible for neurological activity and communication between the senses and intellect), can lead to irregularities in *buddhi*'s functioning.

From an *Ayurvedic* standpoint, the difficulties faced by dyslexic children can be addressed using two terms:

- *Akshara rupatva vishama vijnana* – can be interpreted as defective perception or recognition of letter forms and their phonemic equivalents.
- *Buddhi vishama vijnana* – can be interpreted as defective functioning of the intellect in processing and analyzing perceived information.

These impairments collectively explain the decoding and comprehension challenges seen in dyslexia. They represent not a complete absence of cognitive ability, but a selective dysfunction in the pathway between sensory perception, mental processing, and intellectual integration.

Dyslexia, though not directly described in the classical texts, can be correlated with certain *manasika vikaras* due to its cognitive, perceptual, and learning impairments. When we examine the *samprapti* (pathogenesis) of dyslexia, it becomes evident that the role of *buddhi* is central. While explaining the *samprapti* of *unmada*⁹, have emphasized the derangement of *mana*, *buddhi* and *smrithi* a leading to faulty perception, interpretation, and retention of knowledge. Therefore, it is justifiable to adopt the principles of *unmada chikitsa* while planning a holistic treatment protocol for dyslexia. This approach offers both *yuktivyapashraya* (rational) and *daivavyapashraya* (spiritual/psychological) measures, aiming not only at symptomatic improvement but also at enhancing the child's confidence, learning abilities, and mental stability.

4.4 *Snehapana* and *Shodhana* in Addressing *Manovaha Srotodushti*

Internal oleation with *medhya ghritas* can nourish and strengthen the higher mental faculties. The unctuous, *sneha* property aids in pacifying *vata dosha*, which is predominantly responsible for irregular, unstable, and poor cognitive coordination. The lipid medium of ghee also facilitates better delivery of phytoconstituents across the blood-brain barrier, thereby supporting neurocognitive functions. Appropriate *shodhana* (purificatory) procedures like *nasya* with *medhya taila*, *shirovirechana*, help to improve the clarity of perception, restore the functioning of *buddhi*, and reduce the obstacles to *indriyartha sannikarsha* .

4.5 *Satwajaya chikitsa* – Strengthening the mind through *dhee*, *dhairya*, and *atmavijnana*

Satwajaya chikitsa, one of the prime mental health interventions mentioned in Ayurveda focuses on controlling the mind by restraining it from unwholesome objects and reinforcing positive thought processes. The three key components — *dhee*, *dhairya* (courage) , and *atmavijnana* (self confidence) — are especially relevant in dyslexia management. Structured learning techniques, guided reading sessions, and phoneme-based instructions can be framed as modern parallels to *dhee* strengthening, ensuring rational and logical comprehension.

Children with dyslexia often develop psychological comorbidities like anxiety and depression due to the academic disadvantage. Techniques of reassurance, motivational counselling, and incremental goal setting

help in nurturing *dhairya*, thereby promoting persistence in learning efforts. Cultivating self-awareness through reflective practices, yoga, meditation, and mindfulness games can help the child develop a sense of inner balance.

4.6 Rasayana chikitsa – Enhancing cognitive and intellectual functions

Rasayana chikitsa is a rejuvenative therapy aimed at promoting longevity, immunity, and higher mental faculties such as *medha and smriti*. In the context of dyslexia, where *buddhi vishamavijnana* is observed, *medhya rasayanas* assume a central role. Clinical studies have demonstrated the cognitive-enhancing effects of *Brahmi*, a well-known *Medhya Rasayana*. Roodenrys et al. (2002) reported significant improvement in memory acquisition and retention following chronic *Brahmi* administration, while a systematic review by Pase et al. (2012) concluded that *Bacopa monnieri* supplementation improves memory performance in healthy individuals. Furthermore, a meta-analysis by Kongkeaw et al. (2014) demonstrated significant improvements in cognition, particularly attention and information-processing speed, supporting the traditional role of *Medhya Rasayanas* in enhancing *Buddhi* and cognitive functions. By integrating *rasayana chikitsa* into the treatment regimen, we not only aim at symptomatic relief but also at enhancing the overall mental capacity of the child, enabling better adaptation to academic and social environments.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion the Ayurveda perspective offers a unique understanding of the condition, highlighting the importance of integrating sensory organs, mind, intellect, and consciousness in knowledge acquisition. The present work explains dyslexia through the Ayurvedic framework of *jnanopathikrama*, offering a holistic perspective on cognitive development, knowledge acquisition, and phonemic processing. However, the present views remains largely literature-based and requires scientific validation. Future research should focus on evaluating the efficacy of *medhya rasayana* and other Ayurvedic interventions in improving phonemic awareness and cognitive functions, addressing research questions such as whether Ayurvedic cognitive assessment parameters can be developed and validated as complementary tools for evaluating learning disorder and conducting well-designed clinical and interdisciplinary studies to strengthen evidence and promote integrative management strategies for dyslexia.

Contribution Details

Literature search and manuscript preparation: Deepa P; Concept, design, manuscript editing and manuscript review: Lekshmi M K.

Conflicts of Interest/ Competing Interests

There are no conflicts of interest to disclose.

REFERENCES

1. Privitera AJ, Ng SHS, Chen SHA. Cognitive and neural mechanisms of learning and interventions for improvement across the adult lifespan: A systematic review protocol. PLoS One 2024; 19(5):e0301935. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0301935>.
2. Miller EK, Freedman DJ, Wallis JD. The prefrontal cortex: Categories, concepts and cognition. Philos Trans R Soc B Biol Sci 2002; 357(1424):1123-1136. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2002.1099>
3. Sunil AB, Banerjee A, Divya M, Rathod HK, Patel J, Gupta M. Dyslexia: An invisible disability or different ability. Ind Psychiatry J 2023; 32:S72-S75. https://doi.org/10.4103/ipj.ipj_196_23
4. Schulte-Körne, G. Spezifische Lernstörungen. Zeitschrift Für Kinder- Und Jugendpsychiatrie Und

- Psychotherapie,2014; 42(5):369-374. <https://doi.org/10.1024/1422-4917/a000312>
5. Sharma RK, Dash B. Agnivesa's Charaka Samhita, Sutra Sthana. Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi, 2009.
 6. Sharma RK, Dash B. Sarira Sthana. In: Agnivesa's Charaka Samhita. Reprint, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi, 2010.
 7. Murthy KRS. Susruta Samhita. Vol. 1, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2007.
 8. Di Folco C, Guez A, Peyre H, Ramus F. Epidemiology of developmental dyslexia: A comparison of DSM-5 and ICD-11 criteria. medRxiv 2020; 2020.12.18.20248189. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.12.18.20248189>
 9. Galaburda AM, Cestnick L. Developmental dyslexia. RN 2003; 36(Suppl 1):0-3.
 10. Morton J, Frith U. Causal Modeling: A Structural Approach to Developmental Psychopathology. In: Developmental Psychopathology. Vol. 1, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1995, 357-390.
 11. Fisher SE, Francks C. Genes, cognition and dyslexia: Learning to read the genome. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 2006; 10(6):250-257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2006.04.003>
 12. Nicolson RI, Fawcett AJ, Dean P. Developmental dyslexia: The cerebellar deficit hypothesis. *Trends in Neurosciences* 2001; 24(9):508-511. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0166-2236\(00\)01896-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0166-2236(00)01896-8)
 13. Livingstone MS, Rosen GD, Drislane FW, Galaburda AM. Physiological and anatomical evidence for a magnocellular defect in developmental dyslexia. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 1991; 88(18):7943-7947. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.88.18.7943>
 14. Greatrex JC, Drasdo N. The magnocellular deficit hypothesis in dyslexia: A review of reported evidence. *Ophthalmic & Physiological Optics : The Journal of the British College of Ophthalmic Opticians (Optometrists)* 1995; 15(5):501-506.
 15. Ramus F. Developmental dyslexia: Specific phonological deficit or general sensorimotor dysfunction? *Current Opinion in Neurobiology* 2003; 13(2):212-218. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-4388\(03\)00035-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-4388(03)00035-7)
 16. Wolf M, Bowers PG, Biddle K. Naming-speed processes, timing, and reading: A conceptual review. *Journal of Learning Disabilities* 2000; 33(4):387-407. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002221940003300409>
 17. Wearmouth J, Soler J, Reid G. Meeting difficulties in literacy development: Research, policy and practice. *British Journal of Educational Studies* 2003; 51(3):245-246.
 18. Démonet JF, Taylor MJ, Chaix Y. Developmental dyslexia. *Lancet (London, England)* 2004; 363(9419):1451-1460. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(04\)16106-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(04)16106-0)
 19. Galaburda AM, Sherman GF, Rosen GD, Aboitiz F, Geschwind N. Developmental dyslexia: Four consecutive patients with cortical anomalies. *Annals of Neurology* 1985; 18(2):222-233. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.410180210>
 20. Frith U. Paradoxes in the definition of dyslexia. *Dyslexia* 1999; 5(4):192-214. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-0909\(199912\)5:43.0.CO;2-N](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-0909(199912)5:43.0.CO;2-N)
 21. American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5). Edn 5, American Psychiatric Publishing, Washington DC, 2013.
 22. Darrot G, Gros A, Manera V, De Cara B, Faure S, Corveleyn X et al. Effects of a developmental dyslexia remediation protocol based on the training of audio-phonological cognitive processes in dyslexic children with high intellectual potential: Study protocol for a multiple-baseline single-case experimental design. *BMC Pediatrics* 2023; 23(1):404. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-023-04189-6>
 23. Mishra YC. Padārtha Vijnana (Basic Principles of Ayurveda). Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, 2010.
 24. Srikantamurthy KR. Sutra Sthana. In: Vagbhata's Ashtanga Hridayam. Chaukhamba Krishnadas

Academy, Varanasi, 2013.

25. Jain T, Yadav SK. A study on ajna chakra with special reference to pineal gland. *International Ayurvedic Medical Journal* 2016; 4(6):980-986.http://www.iamj.in/posts/images/upload/980_986.pdf
26. Snow CE. Reading for Understanding: Toward an R&D Program in Reading Comprehension. RAND Corporation, Santa Monica, 2002.
27. Ehri LC. Grapheme–Phoneme Knowledge Is Essential for Learning to Read Words in English. In: Word Recognition in Beginning Literacy. Edn 1, Routledge, London, 1998, 3-38.<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410602718>
28. Ehri LC. Phases of development in learning to read words by sight. *Journal of Research in Reading* 1995;18(2):116–125.[doi:10.1111/j.1467-9817.1995.tb00077.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9817.1995.tb00077.x).
29. Baddeley A. Working memory. *Science*. 1992;255(5044):556–559. [doi:10.1126/science.1736359](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1736359).
30. Shaywitz S. *Overcoming Dyslexia*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press; 2003.

Fig 1. Illustrates the systematic methodology to identify, screen, and select relevant literature for the present review, with phonemic awareness serving as the primary filtering keyword.

Fig 2. Schematic diagram of Ayurveda ethiopathogenesis of Dyslexia.